

POWER GRID WITH EMBEDDED NETWORKED MICROGRIDS

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Annotation : *The international community has set ambitious targets to replace the use of fossil fuels for electricity generation with renewable energy sources. The use of large-scale (e.g., solar farms) and small-scale solutions (e.g., onsite green technologies) represents one way to achieve these goals. This paper presents a mathematical optimization framework to coordinate the energy decisions between the distribution network and the networked microgrids embedded within it. Utility-scale renewable and conventional generators are considered in the distribution network, while the microgrids include onsite renewable generation and energy storage. The distribution network operator utilizes demand-side management policies to improve the network's efficiency, and the microgrids operate under these programs by reducing their energy usage, scheduling the electricity usage under dynamic tariffs, and supplying energy to the grid. The uncertainty of renewable energy sources is addressed by robust optimization.*

Keywords: *demand response; intelligent energy management systems renewable energy integration;*

According to the World Bank [1], between 1960 and 2018 the world's total greenhouse gas emissions increased from 9.46 to 34.04 Gt of CO₂ and the emissions per capita increased from 3.12 to 4.48 metric tons of CO₂. Additionally, electricity consumption increased from 1200.15 to 3128.30 kWh per capita between 1971 and 2014 [1]. To satisfy the growing energy demand, efficient electricity supply systems with a higher capacity are necessary. Nevertheless, a linear increment in the current power generation share, which is mainly composed of fossil fuel sources, will result in an accelerated increase in greenhouse gas concentration. For example, according to the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) [2], the U.S. power grid in 2020 was composed of 60.6% fossil fuels, 19.7% nuclear, and 19.8% renewables. The use of renewable energy sources (RES) to generate electricity is an option to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. As a result, there is a growing environmental awareness in the international community, and in some cases, specific goals have been derived to address this climate change, e.g., the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals [3]. Other international efforts, such as the Paris Agreement, provide quantifiable targets to reduce greenhouse gas emissions or to increase the renewable share of the generation mix. For example, the European Union targets are to generate 27% of the electricity from

renewables by 2030, while the U.S. state of California's targets are 50% by 2030 [4]. Reducing the environmental footprint from global-scale systems requires the participation of both large-scale and small-scale entities. In this context, the utilization of renewable Energies 2022, 15, 2350. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15072350> <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/energies> Energies 2022, 15, 2350 2 of 24 energy to satisfy the electricity demand is aligned with the international community's objectives. Increasing the renewables share in the electricity generation mix can be achieved by two different approaches: (1) By the utilization of large-scale generators, such as wind farms, hydropower, solar farms, and solar concentration; (2) By using multiple small-scale generators owned by the consumers for onsite electricity generation. Each of these approaches presents different advantages and disadvantages. Large-scale generators owned by utility companies allow some control in their operations and more precise forecasts, while from the consumer point of view there will be more to pay in utility bills due to the investment required for these projects and the cost associated with the intermittency. In the case of small-scale solutions, the utility company reduces its control and forecast capabilities over these sources, but it transfers the investment costs to the consumers, while the owners can actively participate in the electricity market due to demand-side management (DSM) policies, the capacity to form microgrids—discussed later in this paper—and reduced electricity bills, even if there is an initial investment. In any case, one of the main challenges of renewable sources compared to conventional generation systems is that they present a higher variability which can jeopardize the grid stability and reliability [5,6], and more advanced control techniques are required to efficiently manage this uncertainty. On the energy policy side, DSM is a series of activities that distribution network operators (DNOs) undertake to change the users' energy consumption pattern to achieve power grid efficiency. For a comprehensive review of DSM policies, see [7–9]. DSM policies can be divided into two categories: energy efficiency and demand response (DR). While energy efficiency proposes policies to reduce the energy consumption, e.g., the replacement of older equipment with efficient equipment, DR utilizes activities in which the consumers can participate to change the load pattern [9]. Laitos et al. [10] mention that the main advantages that DSM policies provide to energy systems include (i) peak shaving, (ii) reduction in operational and capacity costs, (iii) improved system reliability, and (iv) emission reduction via the utilization of greener technologies. These advantages are the result of the consumer's load curve control, carried out in six modalities [9,10]:

- Peak shaving: This aims to reduce the power usage during high-demand periods (peak), either via direct load control or through pricing contracts.
- Valley filling: The goal of this strategy is to encourage consumers to increase their load during periods with low demand (off-peak) to secure the system's stability.
- Load shifting: This consists of shifting the consumers' loads from peak periods to off-peak periods with minimum or no change in the total energy consumption.
- Load growth or load building: The overall consumption

increases during the planning horizon. • Load reduction or energy conservation: The overall consumption during the planning horizon is reduced. • Flexible load curve: The loads can be redistributed during the planning horizon flexibly. The consumers receive benefits for participating in this strategy, while the DNOs have the flexibility to improve the reliability of the system or to respond to emergencies. In general, consumers are interested in two types of DR policies: incentive-based programs, in which the users receive incentives to participate in specific events defined by the grid operator, and price-based programs, which present different electricity tariffs at certain periods depending on the demand level of the grid and the generation cost. The basic price-based program is the Time-of-Use, in which different price tariffs are present in different time blocks; the tariffs are higher during peak periods than during off-peak periods. A modification of this approach, known as Time-and-Level-of-Use (TLOU) [11] also considers the level of consumption at each time block. Other price-based programs are the real-time pricing, in which the tariffs are based on the real-time generation cost, and the critical peak pricing, which imposes very high tariffs during (very short) critical peak periods, e.g., during emergency conditions [8].

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From the consumer side, the evolution in distributed energy resources, defined as demand- and supply-side resources that can be deployed throughout an electric distribution system to meet the energy and reliability needs [12], has changed the nature of the grid from passive to active [13]. These resources, such as roof solar photovoltaic (PV) panels and diesel generators with capacities ranging up to hundreds of MW, small-scale storage cells, electric vehicles, and smart meters, among other technologies, provide the consumers with the opportunity to generate and store energy. Different from utility-scale energy resources, such as coal-based thermal power plants, hydropower, and large-scale solar and nuclear plants, which are centralized and designed to supply energy for long distances, distributed energy resources are located close to the consumption points. This reduces the transmission and generation costs, particularly when the distributed resources are utilized to cover peak periods [14]. Distributed energy technologies allow for the formation of microgrids. A microgrid is defined as a small-scale power system with at least one distributed energy resource and one load, with clearly defined electrical boundaries, and a smart infrastructure that allows self-supply and islanding, providing security, reliability, autonomy, and resilience [14,15]. Microgrid technology lets electricity consumers improve their energy efficiency, including the use of clean energy. Some examples of microgrids include small distribution networks, manufacturing systems, data centers, smart buildings, and other systems that have onsite energy resources. For a comprehensive discussion about microgrids, including architecture, functions, challenges, and opportunities, see the research of Yolda,s et al. [16]. As discussed by Khodaei [15], microgrids offer improved reliability, resiliency, and efficiency, reduction of carbon emissions due to a higher power quality, the utilization of less costly RES, and supply of loads in remote areas.

To achieve the optimal coordination of operational and energetic goals, an EMS is assumed to be installed within each microgrid to jointly optimize the use of energy and its operations. Figure 2 presents the scheme for a microgrid with a central EMS that utilizes information from the operational requirements, as well as the available onsite energy technologies and the DN, finding the optimal operations. It is assumed that each microgrid can generate and store its own electricity, and utilize the electricity from the DN to optimize its processes. The EMS considers information, such as costs and incentives offered by the DN, including the DSM policies, to optimally decide how much energy to purchase or sell to the DN. It is assumed that the microgrid's EMS will produce and communicate the following information to the DNO: To achieve the optimal coordination of operational and energetic goals, an EMS is assumed to be installed within each microgrid to jointly optimize the use of energy and its operations. Figure 2 presents the scheme for a microgrid with a central EMS that utilizes

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1. The amount of energy consumed from the grid at each DT level, $D_{im,k,t}$.
2. The amount of energy sold to the grid under firm and non-firm contracts, $\hat{p}_{F/N m,t}$

3. The amount of electricity consumption willing to reduce, $\hat{q}_{m,k,t}$.

Figure 2. The EMS of microgrids.

The management of a microgrid can be more sophisticated when compared to the distribution network (DN) due to their significantly smaller scale, allowing the potential

to mitigate the effects of resource uncertainty and contingencies [17], particularly when load components are deferrable at some level [18]. By utilizing information and communication technologies, microgrids can coordinate the distributed energy resources and controllable loads efficiently, as well as switch over to islanded mode and operate autonomously for safety purposes [19,20]. Controllable distributed generators within a microgrid are much smaller than the utility-scale ones of the DN, allowing easier switching operations and a more flexible scheduling that can mitigate the impact of the intermittency of the RES [21,22]. Microgrids are connected to the DN through the point of common coupling, a special bus that allows electricity flow in both directions. A sophisticated energy management system (EMS) to monitor, control, and optimize the (onsite and grid) energy resources and find the system's energy balance contributes to the above-mentioned benefits, making the microgrid technology attractive for the operation of diverse systems. For a comprehensive review of microgrids' EMSs, see the research of Battula et al. [14]. The existence of microgrids that are capable of advanced energy-related decisions within the DN allows for the efficient implementation of DR policies. One of the main barriers that prevents achieving this implementation is the lack of effective collaboration and negotiation protocols between the DNO and the operators of the microgrids, considering that the former obtains profits for selling electricity to the latter, while the microgrids seek to minimize their operational costs. This paper proposes (i) a mathematical optimization framework to find the optimal operation of a DN with networked microgrids embedded into it and (ii) a collaboration scheme to coordinate the energy decisions between the DN and the microgrids. It is assumed that the DNO works closely with the operators of large-scale generators that power the network. Therefore, the decisions to be made include the unit commitment of the utility-scale generators, the optimal power flow problem for the DN, the incentives offered to the microgrids, and the bidirectional power flow between the DN and the microgrids to satisfy the network's energy demand. The DNO uses a dynamic pricing scheme, and requests load reductions to the microgrids in exchange for economic incentives. The proposed model allows the microgrids to make their own decisions, considering the dynamic tariff policies and energy consumption reductions requested by the DNO. Additionally, the point of common coupling allows net metering; i.e., the microgrids can sell their power surplus to the DN. Each microgrid includes an EMS that takes into account the energy supply from the DN, the uncertainty related to the onsite renewable generators, the utilization of energy storage, and the DR policies to find the decisions that minimize its operational cost. The DN can utilize the microgrids' energy resources and decisions as a reserve to improve the network's flexibility. The proposed algorithm helps to carry out the collaboration between the DNO and the microgrids in terms of the interchange of energy, and the participation of the microgrids in the DR programs. The main contributions of this paper are: (i) We introduce an optimization model that finds the optimal unit commitment and power flow of a DN with multiple embedded

microgrids, without direct control nor complete information of the microgrids' operations; the uncertainty related to the renewable sources is quantified and incorporated into the model via robust optimization. (ii) A collaboration and negotiation protocol between the DNO and the microgrids to allow the latter to reduce their energy usage, schedule the electricity usage under dynamic tariffs, and supply energy to the grid. (iii) A case study based on a modified instance of the IEEE 30-Bus System is analyzed to show the effectiveness of the proposed approach under different configurations, eliminating the necessity of load shedding and increasing the renewable energy share and power supplied by the microgrids to the distribution network. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Previous work is reviewed in Section 2. In Section 3, the model for the optimal operation of the DNO with multiple embedded microgrids is presented, including the discussion of the uncertainty management and solution algorithm to solve the proposed model and the negotiation protocol.

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